

THE SOCIO-ECONOMIC AND THE HOUSEHOLD AND WASTE GENERATION STATUS IN JALINGO METROPOLIS, TARABA STATE

¹Ubangida Israel Musa, ²Ndidi Ewere Edwin, ¹Rimamnyang Albert Kwena, ³Oliver A. Maima, ¹Adi Timothy Agyo, ⁴Swapam Wallam, ⁵Bagula John Allison, ¹Sambo Iferika and ¹Ojeh Vincent Nduka

¹Department of Geography, Taraba State University, Jalingo

²Department of Geography, University of Delta, Agbor, Delta State

³Department of Geography, College of Education, Zing, Taraba State.

⁴Fatima Diya, Consultant manager, Adamawa State

⁵AGT Department, Adamawa State College of Agriculture, Science and Technology Hong

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Abstract: This study assessed the relationship between households' socioeconomic status and waste generation in Jalingo Metropolis. The study adopted a survey research design. The study was guided by three research questions, two objectives, and two hypotheses. The study was based on the EKC theory and the waste management hierarchy model. Data for the study were obtained from primary and secondary sources. The study population consists of 318,481 people within the Jalingo metropolis. A sample size of 390 respondents was used. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire and visual observation. A total of 384 questionnaires were used for the analysis after data cleaning. The data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using the mean and standard deviation, and the hypotheses were tested using linear regression. The study found a significant influence of household income level on waste generation in Jalingo metropolis ($F=6.558$, $P<0.05$). Similarly, a significant relationship was found between the education level of household members and their waste management practices in Jalingo Metropolis ($F=85.828$, $P<0.05$). The study concludes that socioeconomic status is a major determinant of household waste generation and disposal behaviors in Jalingo. The government should implement and enforce policies that promote proper waste segregation, recycling, and environmentally friendly disposal methods. To ensure effectiveness, policies should be tailored to the waste disposal behaviors of different socioeconomic groups.

Keywords: Solid Waste Generation, Household, Socio-economic status, Jalingo

INTRODUCTION

The generation and disposal of solid waste in developing countries remain among the most persistent challenges that obstruct many developmental initiatives. This concern has been, and is likely to remain, a major focus for policymakers, bureaucrats, educationists, environmentalists, and researchers well into the second quarter of this

century (Ugo & Francis, 2023). At the global level, approximately 1.3 tons of solid waste are produced each year, and this figure is projected to increase to 2.2 tons by 2025. The financial cost is also expected to rise from the present USD 205.4 billion to USD 375.5 billion in 2025 (Hoorweg & Bhada Tata, as cited in Orhorhoro & Oghoghorie, 2019). Historical records indicate that no civilization, ancient or modern, has developed without generating some form of solid waste.

Eurostat (2021) reported that in 2018, approximately 2337 million tons of waste were generated in the EU as a result of economic activities and household consumption. More than half of this waste (54.6%) was managed through recovery processes: recycling (37.9%), backfilling (10.7%), or energy recovery (6.0%). The remaining portion (45.4%) was either disposed of in landfills (38.4%), incinerated without energy recovery (0.7%), or managed through other means (6.3%) (Cosimo & Pasquale, 2022). MSW accounts for only about 10% of the total waste generated, but it demonstrates a highly varied and complex composition due to multiple sources and its strong link to unsustainable consumption patterns (Cosimo & Pasquale, 2022). Significant differences exist among EU member states in terms of the waste treatment methods applied (Castillo Giménez, Montañés, & Tadeo, 2019).

The landfilling of MSW remains one of the most widely used disposal methods, although this unsustainable practice has been declining in developed countries. To accelerate this shift, the EU adopted a new circular economy action plan in March 2020, introducing a mix of legislative and non-legislative measures aimed at sectors where coordinated action at the EU level can generate significant added value (Cosimo & Pasquale, 2022). These measures include new targets intended to close the product life cycle loop. In line with this, the EU has set objectives that include raising the recycling rate of municipal waste to at least 65% by 2035 and reducing the amount of waste sent to landfill to no more than 10% by weight (European Environment Agency, 2021).

According to a 2024 study in India, the country's rapid urbanization and economic development are worsening its waste crisis. Ashutosh, Vasanth, and Karthigaiselvan (2024) found that a household's income and education level are major factors in this dynamic. Contrary to what some might expect, lower-income households generate a larger amount of waste, whereas higher education levels strongly predict better recycling habits.

In 2012, Africa was already generating approximately 125 million tons of municipal solid waste (MSW) annually, with sub-Saharan Africa contributing approximately 81 million tons, or 65% of the total (United Nations Environment program, 2018; Gebremedhin, Oelofse, & Godfrey, 2018). However, only about 55% of this waste, roughly 68 million tons, is actually collected. This means that nearly half of the MSW produced is left unmanaged, often dumped on pavements, in open fields, or into storm water drains and rivers, where it poses serious health and environmental risks (Gebremedhin et al., 2018).

In Nigeria, the problem is especially visible in urban centers, where waste volumes continue to rise sharply. Emerging urban areas such as Jalingo are not exempt; growing market pressures and the spread of consumerism have also fueled higher levels of waste generation. What makes the issue worse is that many people remain unaware of the negative consequences of poor waste management for their health, livelihoods, and the environment (Ibiwumi et al., 2024).

SES refers to the social and economic position of an individual or group within a society (Munir, Faiza, Jamal, Daud, & Iqbal, 2023). It is usually assessed through a combination of factors, such as income, occupation, and education level, as well as additional indicators, such as housing quality or access to essential resources and services (Munir, Faiza, Jamal, Daud, & Iqbal, 2023). Understanding socioeconomic status is crucial in several

fields, including waste generation studies, as it highlights inequalities that may exist between different social and economic groups. Socioeconomic conditions often shape consumption patterns, influencing purchasing power, lifestyle choices, and access to goods and services (Ashutosh, Vasanth, & Karthigaiselvan, 2024). Higher income groups typically consume more and may therefore produce larger volumes of waste than lower income groups. These socioeconomic factors also affect the nature and composition of waste generated (Zhao, Diunugala, & Mombeuil, 2021). For instance, households with higher incomes may spend more on packaged goods and luxury products, leading to greater waste generation (Zhao, Diunugala, & Mombeuil, 2021). In contrast, households with lower incomes may depend more on essential items and have limited access to a variety of goods, resulting in different waste profiles (Zhao, Diunugala, & Mombeuil, 2021).

Socioeconomic status can also shape the adopted methods of waste disposal. Limited access to adequate waste management services results in improper practices such as open dumping or burning in some low-income communities (Rabail, Nabeela, Naheed, & Nosheen, 2024). Such practices pose serious risks to human health and the environment. The relationship between SES and waste generation can be assessed through composition studies, waste audits, statistical data, surveys, questionnaires, and commercial reports. McDonald and Smithers (2018) found that, on average, approximately 15% of the solid waste sent to landfill each year originates from construction activities in Australia. Similarly, a survey conducted in Scotland (Scottish Environment Protection Agency, 2008) indicated that the retail, wholesale, hotel, and restaurant sectors were the largest generators of commercial waste in 2006. The survey also highlighted that regions with a higher concentration of businesses produced substantially greater amounts of business waste than those with fewer enterprises (Amasuomo & Baird, 2019).

Waste management has become an urgent concern in many urban centers, particularly in developing nations such as Nigeria. Rapid urbanization and population growth in Jalingo Metropolis, the capital of Taraba State, recently have led to increased levels of waste generation. Therefore, effective waste management is vital for safeguarding public health, ensuring environmental sustainability, and maintaining the esthetic quality of urban spaces. Urbanization refers to the movement of people from rural areas to towns and cities in search of improved economic opportunities, political stability, education, healthcare, and other essential amenities. This process results in greater population concentration in urban areas and transforms living, working, and social interaction patterns. While urbanization can foster economic growth, cultural diversity and innovation, it also presents significant challenges, including housing shortages, poverty, environmental degradation and increased waste generation. Waste generation denotes the quantity of waste produced by households over a defined period. The volume and type of waste generated vary across socioeconomic groups and are shaped by factors such as consumption patterns, lifestyle choices, and waste management approaches. Key influences on waste generation include household size, income levels that affect purchasing behaviour, access to waste disposal services, recycling practices, and environmental awareness levels (Kuddus, Tynan, & McBryde, 2020).

The SES of households plays a vital role in shaping waste generation patterns. SES is a composite indicator comprising income, education, occupation, and social standing, all of which influence household behaviours, consumption trends, and waste management practices (Bakare & Babatunde, 2022). Households with higher incomes often generate more waste because of greater consumption, whereas those with lower incomes may produce less waste but face challenges in proper disposal due to inadequate access to waste management services. Therefore, socioeconomic status encompasses a range of factors, including income levels, educational attainment,

occupational status, and living conditions. These determinants can significantly affect waste generation in a particular area. Households with higher socioeconomic status generally consume more goods and products, leading to increased packaging, consumer items, and other disposable materials waste. Conversely, households with lower socioeconomic status may generate larger proportions of organic waste, reflecting dietary patterns and limited reliance on processed or packaged food. Empirical studies indicate a positive correlation between SES and waste generation levels (Bakare & Babatunde, 2022).

Waste generation and disposal remain pressing global environmental concerns. Rapid population growth, industrialization, and the use of chemicals to boost agricultural productivity have posed hazards to human health and contributed to environmental degradation, particularly in urban settings. Many districts of Taraba State, especially those with high levels of activity, have limited access to structured waste management services. Consequently, waste is often left unattended, buried, or burned without consideration of its adverse consequences. Neglecting waste for extended periods creates serious health risks, produces unpleasant odours, contaminates groundwater sources, and diminishes the cleanliness and visual quality of the environment. A large share of solid waste in the form of packaging materials, such as polythene, cans, bottles, and cardboard, arises from cross-border commercial activity. The state's formal economy is dominated by banking, retail, and the freight industry, whereas the informal sector is driven by auto mechanics, food vendors, traders in mobile phone accessories, and second-hand clothing markets.

In urban areas, such as Jalingo Metropolis, waste management has emerged as a significant challenge, largely because of the rising volume of household waste. The SES of households is assumed to play an important role in shaping the patterns of waste generation. Nevertheless, the exact nature of this relationship in the Jalingo Metropolis remains poorly understood.

Households with higher socioeconomic status may generate larger volumes of waste due to higher consumption levels, whereas households with lower socioeconomic status may produce less waste but face difficulties in accessing formal waste disposal services. Lower-status households may also generate a different waste composition, particularly organic waste, owing to limited access to processed or packaged goods. These variations complicate waste management planning and may result in inefficient resource allocation for waste collection and disposal.

No systematic study has investigated how socioeconomic gaps influence the production of waste in the Jalingo Metropolis. This knowledge gap limits the ability to develop targeted waste management policies that address the socioeconomic groups' varying needs. Against this backdrop, this study aims to investigate the relationship between household socioeconomic level and garbage generation in Jalingo Metropolis. Having a better knowledge of this link is critical for designing effective waste management policies that enhance environmental sustainability and improve the region's public health outcomes.

The study was guided by three (3) research questions, viz, What are the socioeconomic factors influencing waste generation in Jalingo Metropolis? How does household income level influence waste generation in Jalingo Metropolis? What is the relationship between household members' education level and their waste management practices in Jalingo Metropolis?

The specific objectives of this study are to identify the socio-economic factors influencing waste generation in Jalingo Metropolis, investigate the influence of household income level on waste generation in Jalingo

Metropolis, and assess the relationship between household members' education level and their waste management practices in Jalingo Metropolis.

The study developed and tested two (2) null hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance:

HO₁: No significant influence of household income level on waste generation in Jalingo Metropolis.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between household members' education level and their waste management practices in Jalingo Metropolis.

Recognizing how socioeconomic status influences waste generation can equip Jalingo Metropolis policymakers with practical insights for creating more effective and targeted waste management strategies. For example, policies and programs could be tailored to address the specific needs of low-income neighborhoods, particularly where regular waste collection services are limited.

By identifying the socioeconomic factors that contribute to higher levels of waste generation, this study could assist local authorities in strengthening waste management practices. Such measures may include promoting recycling initiatives in higher-income areas or enhancing waste collection infrastructure in lower-income communities.

The findings of this study could help inform broader measures targeted at enhancing environmental sustainability in Jalingo Metropolis. Addressing social inequalities in waste generation and management can reduce the total environmental impact of a city.

2. Conceptual Clarification

2.1 Concept of the Waste

Waste is an unavoidable outcome of human activities (Nathanson, 2020). Substances or objects that no longer serve a useful function and are therefore disposed of, intended for disposal, or mandated for incineration under national legislation (Rahman & Alam, 2020). The term solid waste encompasses "any garbage, refuse, sludge from a waste treatment plant, water supply treatment plant, or air pollution control facility and other discarded material, including solid, liquid, semisolid, or contained gaseous material, arising from industrial, commercial, mining, agricultural, and community activities" (Shaghayegh & Mahdi, 2023).

Human activity inevitably generates waste (Brunner & Rechberger, 2014), and concerns about its production have existed since prehistoric times (Amasuomo & Baird, 2020). In recent decades, both the rate and quantity of waste generation have dramatically increased, along with greater diversity in the types of waste produced (Vergara & Tchobanoglous, 2012). Unlike in prehistoric periods, when small populations and abundant land allowed the environment to absorb waste without serious harm, today, waste poses major ecological and health risks (Sakariyau, Ridwan, & Sadiq, 2022).

A watershed moment in waste generation occurred in the sixteenth century, when the Industrial Revolution spurred large-scale migration from rural to urban regions (Wilson, as cited in Uzoagu & Eheazu, 2022). Rapid population expansion resulted in significant increases in garbage volume and diversity. Metals and glass originally appeared in substantial amounts in municipal trash streams (Williams, 2020). Overcrowded cities saw extensive waste and open dumping, which became breeding sites for rats and vermin, posing major public health risks. Epidemics with significant death rates were quickly followed. By the 18th century, public officials were forced to implement controlled waste disposal systems to preserve public health (Tchobanoglous, Theisen, & Vigil, as cited in Sakariyau, Ridwan, & Sadiq, 2022).

In contrast, rapid urbanization and economic growth in developing countries create conditions similar to those that industrialized nations struggled with in earlier centuries (Wilson, as cited in Uzoagu & Eheazu, 2022). Recent studies highlight the urgent need for sustainable waste management to prevent comparable public health crises (Chakraborty & Maity, 2020; Tanveer, Khan, & Umar, 2022; Adeniji & Oluwatoyin, 2024). Most developed nations eventually undergo a phase of environmental reform, and many have largely resolved the health and environmental issues associated with waste generation.

A key question in contemporary discussions is: what truly defines waste? Waste can be understood as an unwanted byproduct of human activity that often contains the same components as useful products (Hossain, Islam, Ghose, & Sahajwalla, 2022). According to Li, Jin, Borrion, and Li (2019), waste also refers to materials that individuals seek to discard, even when they must incur disposal costs. Although waste generation is inevitable, it highlights inefficiencies in production systems because its constant creation represents the ongoing loss of valuable resources (Uzoagu & Eheazu, 2022).

Importantly, what one individual discards as waste may be valued as a resource. Therefore, a material becomes waste only when its owner identifies it as such, highlighting the subjective nature of the concept (Uzoagu & Eheazu, 2022). Nevertheless, having precise definitions of waste is essential because they form the foundation of regulatory systems that safeguard human health and the environment in which waste is managed or disposed of (European Environment Agency, 2021). Present regulations emphasize the circular economy model, which seeks to reduce waste, extend the lifespan of materials, and encourage reuse and recycling to reduce environmental harm (European Environment Agency, 2021).

Globally, waste generation and management remain pressing environmental challenges, particularly in urban centers. Household waste volumes, shaped by socioeconomic factors, are rapidly rising, leading to environmental degradation, health hazards, and management difficulties. Evidence shows that strategies such as recycling, composting, and waste-to-energy technologies can mitigate these impacts and promote sustainable development (Ashutosh, Vasanth, & Karthigaiselvan, 2024; Zhang et al., 2019).

Population growth and urbanization are key drivers of this trend, pushing solid waste generation upward. This is especially evident in countries such as Ghana, where municipal authorities often lack the capacity to keep pace with the rising demand for waste services. Alarmingly, global waste volumes are increasing faster than urbanization itself, while urban growth is outstripping the ability of cities to provide basic waste services (Hoorweg & Bhada Tata, 2019). William et al. (2019) further observed that rising living standards and technological advances are accelerating waste generation.

In Africa, including Nigeria, solid waste management continues to face persistent challenges, driven by rapid urbanization, population growth, and inadequate infrastructure. In Nigeria, rural households often rely on open dumping, backyard burning, and composting, while urban areas face challenges of uncollected waste, blocked drains, and overburdened municipal services (Ogwueleka, 2009; Abila & Kantola, 2013; Solomon, 2011). Problems include irregular and inconsistent data collection, insufficient funding, outdated technologies, weak policy frameworks, and poor enforcement and monitoring. A lack of public awareness and participation further compounds the problem (Vinti & Vaccari, 2024; Ferronato & Torretta, 2019).

In Lagos, one of Nigeria's largest cities, the situation is further complicated by residents' reluctance to pay for waste services, the collapse of recycling facilities, and unsafe conditions for waste collectors (Kehinde, 2023). Addressing these issues requires locally tailored solutions, such as considering residents' income levels,

encouraging proper waste sorting and recycling, upgrading dumpsites to sanitary landfills, adopting modern treatment technologies, and strengthening public education initiatives (David, favor, & Sunday, 2020).

Although waste generation rates are lower and management less complex in rural areas, common practices such as open burning and rudimentary composting still pose environmental risks. Overall, achieving sustainable solid waste management in Nigeria requires an integrated approach that combines stronger governance, improved public awareness, and the adoption of innovative technologies (Vinti & Vaccari, 2024; Bakare & Babatunde, 2022).

2.1.1 Classification of the Waste

Waste exists in various forms and can be categorized in multiple ways. Typical criteria used for classification include the physical state, inherent properties, potential for reuse, biodegradability level, generation source, and extent of environmental impact (Honey & Satya, 2019). The World Health Organization (2022) categorizes waste into three types according to physical state: liquid, solid, and gaseous. Although specific systems differ across countries, these three categories are the most widely applied.

Solid waste consists of solid household garbage, industrial residues, and construction debris. Plastics, paper, metals, and other materials that are not liquid (World Health Organization, 2022). Liquid waste refers to wastewater generated from households, industries, and agricultural activities, such as sewage, surface runoff, and chemical effluents released in liquid form (World Health Organization, 2022). Gaseous waste arises from industrial processes, motor vehicles, and other human activities that emit pollutants into the atmosphere in gaseous form (World Health Organization, 2022).

2.1.2 Sources and types of waste

Human activities unavoidably produce waste in various forms, making its management a longstanding environmental concern. As Brunner and Rechberger (2014) noted, virtually all human activities generate waste. Historically, during prehistoric times, waste was primarily regarded as a minor nuisance rather than a pressing environmental problem because populations were smaller and land was abundant, allowing the environment to absorb waste without severe consequences (Harrison, 2023; Tchobanoglous et al., as cited in Harrison, 2023). The dynamics of waste generation shifted dramatically throughout the sixteenth century, with the start of the Industrial Revolution. Large-scale migration from rural to urban areas drove rapid population expansion, increasing both the volume and complexity of urban trash. Metals and glass were first found in significant quantities in municipal rubbish (Williams, Uzoagu, & Eheazu, 2022). The growing population in cities also fostered indiscriminate dumping, which provided breeding sites for mice and other pests, generating major public health concerns.

i. Solid Waste:

MSW is the well-studied of all waste sources. White, Franke, and Hindle (as cited in Shamshad, Raheel, Syed, Nazir, & Muhammad, 2022) emphasized that MSW has important ramifications, especially because it is the most frequently seen waste stream by the public. Political leaders and municipal authorities frequently prioritize the collection, treatment, and disposal of waste. MSW is sourced from numerous sources, including homes, offices, hotels, stores, schools, and other organizations. Its main components include food waste, paper, plastics, rags, metals, and glass. In many situations, municipal waste streams contain demolition and construction debris as well as tiny volumes of hazardous trash, including spent batteries, light bulbs, vehicle parts, and discarded chemicals or pharmaceuticals (World Bank, 2022).

Municipal solid waste (MSW) is commonly understood as refuse collected by municipal authorities, including household waste, non-hazardous waste from industrial, commercial, and institutional activities, and non-infectious hospital waste (Prakash, Gopi, & Ram, 2023). Vergara and Tchobanoglous, as cited in Tadenikawo (2023), emphasized that MSW reflects the communities' cultural habits and lifestyles. They also cautioned that the poor management of MSW creates serious risks to public health and the environment.

Within the European Union, the Landfill Directive formally defines MSW as household waste together with other forms of waste that are similar in nature or composition to domestic refuse. This definition also applies to commercial waste streams, provided that they share characteristics comparable with household waste (Tadenikawo, 2023).

One of the greatest challenges in managing MSW is its heterogeneous composition. According to Id and Rai (2020), MSW typically contains a mix of metals, paper, glass, and organic matter. Honey and Satya (2019) further noted that MSW characteristics vary widely depending on its source. For example, in Turkey, more than half of the MSW consists of biodegradable organic matter, whereas recyclable items such as cardboard, paper, glass, and plastics constitute a substantial portion.

According to Ezudu, Ozoegwu, and Madu (2019), MSW often contains soil, garden and food waste, wood, paper, ashes, plastics, textiles, and rubber. They concluded that households and commercial establishments are its primary sources of income. Similarly, Navarro and Vincenzo (2019) emphasized that MSW generally includes food and garden waste, textiles, paper or cardboard, plastics, glass, and metals. Given this composition, they argued that MSW has a strong potential for energy recovery or fuel conversion. White, Franke, and Hindle (as cited in Tadenikawo, 2023) stressed that unlike other more uniform waste streams, the composition of MSW is highly variable and tends to differ widely between cities and countries.

ii. Agricultural solid waste

Agricultural waste arises from various farming activities, including livestock rearing, crop cultivation, and milk production. Waste typically consists of plant residues, animal manure, and other byproducts produced during agricultural processes. Effective management of agricultural waste is crucial not only to minimize environmental impacts, such as soil and water pollution, but also to harness its potential as a valuable resource. Properly handled, agricultural waste can be transformed into compost, biogas, and biofuels, thereby contributing to soil fertility, reducing GHG emissions, and supporting circular economy initiatives (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations [FAO], 2020).

Agricultural waste has recently gained prominence as a resource in both the energy and industrial sectors. Plant leftovers, animal manure, and other byproducts are increasingly being recycled using anaerobic digestion, biomass conversion, and composting. These methods enable the conversion of agricultural waste into renewable energy and raw materials for industrial use, thereby encouraging a more circular and sustainable economy (EU, 2020). This strategy not only eliminates waste but also provides alternative energy sources and industrial inputs, reinforcing the link between agriculture and sustainability.

However, improper agricultural waste handling can create serious environmental hazards. Sadi and Holm Nielsen, as cited in Amasuomo and Baird (2019), observed that the excessive use of manure on farmland can contaminate both surface water and groundwater. This highlights the urgent need for sustainable agricultural waste management approaches that safeguard the environment while supporting agricultural productivity.

iii. Commercial waste

Commercial waste is one of the major waste streams in the world, accounting for a large portion of the solid waste generated. In Northern Ireland, for example, commercial and industrial activities generated approximately 1.5 million tons of solid trash in 2005, with commercial operations accounting for more than half of the total (Environment and Heritage Service, as cited in Amasuomo & Baird, 2019). Similarly, a 2006 survey in Scotland found that the retail, wholesale, hotel, and restaurant sectors generated the most commercial trash. Regions with higher concentrations of enterprises, such as Glasgow and Clyde, produced disproportionately more waste than less commercialized areas. Overall, the business sector accounted for almost 29% of the total regulated trash in Scotland (Amasuomo & Baird, 2019).

Commercial solid waste refers to both solid and semi-solid waste generated by businesses such as shops, restaurants, marketplaces, offices, hotels, motels, print shops, service stations, and car repair shops (FAO, 2017; World Bank, 2018; Oguntoyinbo, 2012). Because of its composition similar to household waste, this waste stream is frequently classified as MSW (Benjamin, Oguche, & Duvuna, 2019). Consumer electronics, batteries, tires, household appliances, paper, cardboard, metals, plastics, food waste, lumber, and glass are common commercial wastes (Tchobanoglous, quoted in Benjamin et al., 2019).

Sustainable solid waste management requires a thorough understanding of the characteristics, sources, and generation rates of commercial trash. Separating commercial trash enables the identification of its unique composition and volume, resulting in more effective management solutions.

Traditional and Open Markets:

Open market trading is common in many developing countries and serves as a major center of commerce. However, these markets often generate substantial amounts of food waste because of spoilage and unsold items. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (2023), around one-third of worldwide food production is lost, with traditional markets contributing significantly due to inadequate storage and handling mechanisms. The World Health Organization (2024) similarly observed that markets in developing countries often lack adequate disposal infrastructure, resulting in environmental pollution and public health risks. Inefficiencies such as outdated logistics practices further compound these problems, increasing vendors' costs and reducing consumer access to fresh goods (World Bank, 2023). To mitigate these issues, technologies such as smart refrigeration and waste tracking systems are being introduced. Market waste, primarily food, is often indiscriminately dumped and represents the second largest contributor to MSW after household waste (Aye & Widjaya, 2023).

Hotels and Restaurants:

The hospitality industry significantly contributes to waste generation, producing large volumes of refuse daily. In the UK, many small hotels were found to lack environmentally sustainable practices, with most operators failing to implement waste reuse strategies (Andryanto, 2021). A Hong Kong study revealed that the reluctance of hoteliers to adopt recycling stemmed from the cost of recycling materials and a lack of awareness about the environmental impacts of waste. On average, hotels generate more waste than households, with the type and quantity of waste depending on factors such as the number of rooms and involvement in event hosting (Eugenio, Juan, & Noemi, 2023). Waste in hotels often originates from kitchens, restaurants, guest rooms, offices, laundries, and gardens and commonly consists of food waste, plastics, paper, paints, used batteries, and garden refuse (Trung & Kumar, as cited in Amasuomo & Baird, 2019). In Ankara, Gaurav, Peter, and Hawkins (2021) found that hotel waste primarily comprises paper, plastics, metals, glass, and food waste.

Retail Waste:

Retail activities generate large amounts of waste, particularly packaging and perishable items. Honey and Satya (2019) noted that retail waste is mostly nonmetallic, consisting of packaging materials, food residues, and other organic waste, with the type of waste determined by the products sold. A survey of grocery stores in Quebec, Canada, revealed that fruits, baked products, seafood, and packaging materials contributed substantially to retail waste. In the UK, retailing activities generated approximately 1.4 million tons of packaging and food waste in 2008, while in Northern Ireland, commercial sectors, including retail, wholesale, real estate, and public administration, produced approximately 459,285 tons in 2005 (Honey & Satya, 2019). In Mexicali, Mexico, a single store generates 5,375-kg cartons and 339-kg plastics per week (Amasuomo & Baird, 2020). In Quebec, a supermarket chain spends nearly \$6 million annually on waste disposal, leading researchers to recommend recycling and reuse strategies to reduce operational costs (Amasuomo & Baird, 2020).

2.1.4 Factors influencing waste generation

The rate of waste generation is shaped by a range of factors and is largely determined by a particular area's geographical location, customs, climate, living conditions, and economic standards. Consequently, the characteristics, quantity, volume, and composition of SS differ not only across countries but also between urban and rural communities (Yogalakshmi, 2023).

Population size remains one of the most important waste generation determinants. As the population grows, so does the rate of waste production. Nations with large populations generally report higher waste generation per capita. Population increases the volume of waste produced, with densely populated areas generating more waste than sparsely populated ones. Developed countries typically produce more waste due to the abundance of consumer goods. Age composition also plays a role, as younger and older populations may differ in both the type and volume of waste generated (Yogalakshmi, 2023).

Migration patterns between rural and urban areas are another major waste generation driver. Migration in search of employment and education fuels urbanization and industrialization, leading to higher waste levels in cities. For example, in India, an estimated 100,000 people migrate daily from rural to urban centers, with a migration rate of approximately 3.6% annually. Urban centers produce diverse forms of waste, including plastics, paper, packaging materials, food waste, and e-waste, whereas rural waste streams remain relatively small, often dominated by agricultural residues and other biodegradable materials (Yogalakshmi, 2023).

Economic status and lifestyle. Economic conditions strongly influence the rate and type of waste generated. High-income households and nations typically produce greater volumes of solid waste, largely due to higher consumption levels and increased reliance on processed and packaged goods. Urbanization and rising incomes significantly contribute to the production of packaging materials, textiles, electronic devices, furniture, and other waste streams (Amasuomo & Baird, 2020).

Geographical Location. Geographic conditions also play a crucial role, particularly in relation to seasonal and agricultural waste. For example, large volumes of yard waste are generated in regions with extended autumn seasons. In northern India, yard waste generation peaks in February and March, while agricultural waste reaches its highest levels during the harvest period. Geography also influences waste collection; for instance, settlements at higher altitudes may experience waste accumulation due to reduced collection frequency. Tourist destinations often experience seasonal spikes in waste due to the influx of visitors (Yogalakshmi, 2023).

2.1.5 Health Effects of Waste Generation and Disposal

According to Donald et al. (2021), the health impacts of ineffective household solid waste management can be categorized into physical, biological, noncommunicable, psychosocial, and ergonomic risks. Contaminated soil, air, and water provide breeding grounds for flies, rodents, and insect pests. These vectors transmit several diseases, including diarrhea, dysentery, gastrointestinal infections, worm infestations, food poisoning, dengue fever, cholera, leptospirosis, and bacterial infections. They may cause skin, nasal, and ocular irritation as well as respiratory complications.

Exposure to gases emitted by landfills, such as methane, carbon dioxide, sulfur dioxide, and nitrogen dioxide, can cause inflammation, bronchoconstriction, and immune cell dysfunction. Hydrogen chloride and fluoride can lodge in the respiratory system, causing coughing, chest tightness, and dyspnoea. Noncommunicable illnesses are also associated with improper waste management. Pollution from dump sites has been linked to malignancies of the liver, pancreas, kidney, and larynx, as well as non-Hodgkin lymphoma. Other health consequences include birth deformities, preterm births, congenital diseases, and Down syndrome.

In addition to physical and biological impacts, poor waste management contributes to psychosocial problems, including offensive odors, unsightly waste, and stress-related psychological issues. Ergonomic health risks are particularly relevant for waste workers, who face musculoskeletal strain due to poor posture, repetitive movements, and physically demanding tasks (Jutta & Sayed, 2018).

In Malaysia, household trash is mostly organic with a high moisture content, making management and source separation crucial. However, rising garbage volumes and limited landfill capacity have prompted concerns about the sustainability of landfill-based MSW procedures. According to Aminuddin and Rahman (2015), the low level of public participation in waste management stems from the NIMBY ("not in my backyard") attitude and the assumption that municipalities are primarily responsible for solid waste. Consequently, informal waste pickers are responsible for most segregation, which is necessary for survival and extra revenue. While this benefits livelihoods, it also exposes people to substantial health hazards and intensifies socioeconomic vulnerabilities (Donald et al., 2021).

Open dumping, prolonged storage at collection or transfer stations, and improper waste handling further increase human and animal health risks. Occupational hazards also arise during transportation, accidents, and processing activities (Siddiqua et al., 2022). Waste dumps act as pathogen reservoirs, creating favorable conditions for vectors and stray animals. Workers who come into contact with waste are at risk of contracting diseases transmitted by flies, mosquitoes, and animals such as rats, cats, dogs, cows, and pigs (Faruk et al., 2019). Epidemics may occur when these vectors transport pathogens to humans, spreading diseases such as typhoid, salmonellosis, gastroenteritis, dysentery, malaria, filariasis, and dengue. The life cycle of flies, which thrive in decomposing organic waste, underscores the importance of preventive measures, including timely waste collection, regular cleaning of storage bins, covering of waste, and controlled disposal.

Stagnant water accumulating in broken containers, tires, and furniture provides mosquitoes with breeding grounds. Improved sanitation and hygiene practices can significantly reduce the incidence of mosquito-borne diseases. Cockroaches are also vectors of typhoid, cholera, and amebiasis in areas with poor solid waste management. Rodents, such as rats, transmit diseases, including plague, murine typhus, leptospirosis, histoplasmosis, rat-bite fever, salmonellosis, and trichinosis, as waste dumps provide food and shelter. When fed untreated solid waste,

pigs may spread diseases such as trichinosis, cysticercosis, and toxoplasmosis, which are often transmitted to humans through raw or inadequately cooked infected pork (Faruk et al., 2019).

Workers involved in waste collection and processing face occupational hazards, including injuries from sharp objects, such as syringes, broken glass, and blades. Containers with sharp edges can also cause cuts, and exposure to contaminated waste can lead to skin infections and bloodstream diseases. Dust affects the eyes, and inhalation of toxic gases from burning waste is linked to chronic respiratory conditions and cancers (World Health Organization [WHO], 2020).

Moreover, accidents associated with waste handling pose serious risks. Lifting and transporting waste containers can cause musculoskeletal strain, while road dust and smoke from burning waste impair visibility and increase accident risks. Chemical burns occur when workers come into contact with hazardous substances such as pesticides and solvents. Methane explosions at landfill sites remain a serious safety concern. Furthermore, the improper disposal of lead-acid, nickelcadmium, and mercuric oxide batteries exposes both children and adults to significant health risks (WHO, 2020).

2.1.6 Effect of waste on the environment

The increasing volume and complexity of waste generated by modern economies pose significant risks to ecosystems and human health. Globally, an estimated 11.2 billion tons of solid waste are collected each year, with the decomposition of organic matter alone contributing about 5% of total greenhouse gas emissions. Electronic and electrical waste, which contains hazardous and complex substances, has emerged as the fastest-growing challenge in both developed and developing nations.

Ineffective waste management practices, including inadequate collection systems and poor disposal methods, intensify these risks. Unsanitary landfills and open dumping not only contaminate air, soil, and water resources but also threaten public health by polluting drinking water, spreading infections, and facilitating disease transmission. Furthermore, the dispersal of solid waste disrupts ecosystems, while industrial and electronic waste adds further pressure to urban populations and the environment (Siddiqua, Hahladakis, & AlAttiya, 2022).

2.1.7 Measures to Control Waste Generation

i. Reusable bottle/cup for beverages on-the-go

You may already own a reusable water bottle, but do you consistently use it? Regularly carrying a reusable bottle not only helps save money but also reduces waste. By bringing your own water, you are less likely to purchase costly beverages while on the move, thereby avoiding the single-use containers in which they are typically sold. Although many bottles and cans are recyclable, their production, transportation to bottling facilities, and subsequent distribution to retailers consume considerable amounts of energy (Trimble, 2022).

ii. Reusable grocery bags, not just for groceries

Many individuals already have reusable grocery bags similar to reusable water bottles, but they are frequently left at home. Simple methods, such as writing BAGS at the top of your shopping list as a reminder or keeping the bags in the back seat of your car, can help you avoid forgetting them. In addition to lowering reliance on single-use plastic bags, several supermarkets provide small financial incentives, such as a five-cent rebate per bag, allowing customers to save money while helping to reduce trash (Trimble, 2022).

iii. Composting

Up to 25% of household waste is projected to be diverted from landfills and composted at home. Compostable items include fruit and vegetable scraps, eggshells, coffee grounds, grass clippings, and leaves. Composting

requires more effort than other lifestyle changes, but it provides considerable long-term benefits. Depending on the environment, compost can be used as a natural soil enhancer in gardens in 3–12 months. This lowers dependency on chemical fertilizers and, for those who cultivate their own vegetables, can result in higher crop yields. Furthermore, the organic matter in compost serves as a sponge, holding water and thus lowering the irrigation frequency. This conserves water while also saving money and time (Trimble, 2022).

iv. Avoiding single-use food and drink containers and utensils

Avoid using single-use coffee cups, disposable cutlery, straws, and napkins wherever feasible. Many cafés and eateries even offer discounts to clients who bring their own reusable mugs. Keeping a set of washable silverware, including a plate, bowl, and cup, at work is a useful alternative to disposables. Plastic straws can be eliminated or replaced with reusable metal alternatives. Notably, many of these disposable items are made of plastic, are delivered by trucks, and end up in landfills after just one use. Any endeavor to reduce dependency on these items has a significant environmental impact (Journey, 2024).

v. Second-hand items and donated used goods

Before acquiring new products, explore second-hand options, which can result in significant cost savings. This may involve purchasing clothing from charity shops such as Goodwill, collecting old furniture or recycled construction materials from stores such as Habitat for Humanity’s Restore, or scouring internet platforms such as Craigslist for low-cost solutions such as bicycles. Purchasing used products not only minimizes the amount of waste sent to landfills but also benefits local charity and community activities (Journey, 2024).

vi. Shop local farmers’ markets and buy in bulk to reduce packaging costs

Shopping at local farmers’ markets has numerous benefits. Not only does it help local farmers, but it also ensures that consumers have access to fresher products than those commonly found in large shops. Locally produced food does not require long-distance transit or prolonged refrigeration, thereby reducing its environmental impact. Farmers’ markets also use minimal packaging, and many vendors welcome returned products, such as berry baskets or egg cartons, for reuse. Packaging waste can be further minimized by buying food in bulk from establishments that allow consumers to bring their own containers (Journey, 2024).

vii. Reduce your use of paper: mail, receipts, and magazines

Many companies now provide billing statements via email in the digital age, with some offering incentives for customers who opt for paperless services. Increasingly, retail stores issue electronic receipts, which are convenient as they are less likely to be misplaced when required for product returns. Similarly, digital magazine subscriptions can be accessed on tablets or computers, often at a lower cost than printed versions. These practices not only reduce paper consumption but also offer consumers greater convenience (Journey, 2024).

2.1.8 Socio-economic status of households

SES is an economic and sociological measure that describes an individual’s or family’s employment experience, access to economic resources, and social standing in comparison to others (Ashutosh, Vasanth, & Karthigaiselvan, 2024). SES has several characteristics, including income, parental education level, occupation, and access to opportunities and resources. When determining a family’s socioeconomic status, household income, education, and jobs are considered. Personal characteristics affect SES at the individual level.

Recent research has also highlighted a less commonly recognized dimension of SES perceived financial stress—which refers to the balance between income and necessary expenses. This can be assessed by determining whether a person ends each month with more than enough, just enough, or insufficient financial resources. Despite this

broader perspective, SES is most frequently employed to describe economic inequality within society. It is commonly categorized into three broad levels based on income, education, and occupation: high, middle, and low.

Education is generally emphasized more strongly within households of higher socioeconomic status and within their surrounding communities. In contrast, in low-income areas, where basic needs such as food, shelter, and safety take precedence, education is often given lower priority. Young people in disadvantaged households are particularly vulnerable to a range of health and social issues, including unintended pregnancies, substance misuse, and obesity. Low poverty and inadequate educational attainment are also important indicators of physical and mental health problems, such as respiratory infections, arthritis, heart disease, and schizophrenia. These health disparities may be linked to workplace environmental factors, but impairments or mental diseases may also contribute to an individual's-poor socioeconomic status.

2.1.8.1 Levels of Household Socio-Economic Status

SES refers to a household's economic and social standing. A household's socioeconomic status (SES) is commonly defined as its social and economic standing compared to others, as measured by various indices. According to Darin-Mattsson, Fors, and Kåreholt (2017), the following main dimensions are typically employed to assess SES:

- i. **Income:** The total earnings of all household members, including wages, salaries, investments, and other income sources.
- ii. **Education:** The highest level of education attained by household members can influence employment opportunities and earning potential.
- iii. **Occupation:** The type of jobs held by household members, which can reflect their professional skills and economic stability.
- iv. **Wealth:** This includes assets such as property, savings, and investments, as well as liabilities such as debts.
- v. **Living Conditions:** The quality of the household's housing, access to basic services (such as clean water and sanitation), and overall living environment are considered.
- vi. **Health:** Access to and quality of health care services and general health status can be important indicators of SES.
- vii. **Social Capital:** The household's network of relationships and social support systems, which can affect economic opportunities and quality of life.

SES is often categorized into three levels (Darin-Mattsson, Fors, & Kåreholt, 2017):

- i. **Low SES:** Lower income, limited education, and limited resources.
- ii. **Middle SES:** Moderate income, medium education level, and average access to resources.
- iii. **High SES:** Higher income, higher education, and greater access to resources and amenities.

2.1.9 Household Classification Based on Waste Generation

Households can be classified according to their waste generation patterns. Here are some common classifications (Dikole & Letshwenyo, 2020):

- i. **Low-Waste Generators:** Households that generate minimal waste, often due to mindful consumption and recycling practices.

- ii. Average Waste Generators: Typical households generate average amounts of waste, including food waste, packaging materials, and paper products.
- iii. High Waste Generators: Households with larger families or high consumption patterns generate significant amounts of waste.
- iv. Multi-Stream Waste Generators: Households that generate various types of waste, such as hazardous waste (batteries, electronics), organic waste (food, yard trimmings), and recyclables (paper, plastic, glass).
- v. Zero-Waste Households: Households that strive to eliminate waste, often through extreme reduction, reuse, and recycling efforts.

Classifying households based on waste generation can help waste management agencies and municipalities develop targeted waste reduction, recycling, and education strategies (Dikole & Letshwenyo, 2020).

2.1.10 Relationship between Waste Generation and Household Socio-Economic Status

Socioeconomic factors play an important role in shaping how households generate and manage waste. For example, Zhao et al. (2021) discovered that rapid economic expansion and urbanization have a significant impact on waste management techniques in Sri Lanka. Their findings lay the groundwork for understanding how shifting socioeconomic dynamics influence household waste behaviors. Similarly, other studies have examined the social components of trash management and found that community views and cultural norms influence how garbage is generated and treated (Social Factors Influencing Household trash Management, 2022).

Kala et al. (2020) provided more evidence by investigating how income levels, education, and urban growth influence both the quantity and type of municipal solid trash produced. This is especially important in cities with a high socioeconomic diversity, such as Chennai. Amaya et al. (2019) discovered similar patterns in Ecuador, demonstrating how differing economic conditions impact household waste management behaviors in distinct ways.

Beyond economic indicators, social norms and household behaviors also affect waste generation. Apolonio and Lacaza (2022) demonstrated that community practices and attitudes significantly influence food waste behaviors. Similarly, Han et al. (2018) investigated domestic waste in developing countries, highlighting how household characteristics, such as family composition and daily practices, are central to determining waste generation and management outcomes.

Some studies have used regression models to analyze the relationship between waste generation and socioeconomic parameters. Income has consistently emerged as the most significant determinant of household waste generation, making it a critical factor in distinguishing between socioeconomic groups. Education also influences the composition of waste, and the strong correlation between income and education demonstrates the extent to which educational attainment is linked to income levels (Teferi, 2022; EPA, 2019).

Households with higher socioeconomic status tend to consume more goods and services, generating more packaging waste, disposable items, and consumer products. In contrast, households with lower socioeconomic status are more likely to produce organic waste, reflecting dietary habits and limited access to processed or packaged food. Thus, waste generation can be defined as the quantity of waste produced by households over a specific period, with different socioeconomic groups generating varying volumes and types of waste depending on lifestyle choices, consumption patterns, and waste management practices (Vimal, Mathiyazhagan, Agarwal, Luthra, & Sivakumar, 2020).

Other socioeconomic determinants, including household size and employment status, also influence municipal solid waste generation rates. Kaza, Yao, Bhada-Tata, and Woerden (2019) observed a positive relationship between household size and the daily volume of waste generated, although some studies have reported lower per capita waste generation in larger households. Employment status is another influential parameter: while an increase in the number of employed family members is positively associated with total household waste generation, the proportion of organic waste within the overall composition has been shown to be reduced. Environmental awareness is also a critical factor, as households with stronger environmental concerns are more inclined to participate in recycling and therefore produce lower overall waste volumes (Jamialahmadi, Hashem, & Jalili, 2022).

2.2 Theoretical Framework

The study is based on the EKC theory (1955)

The EKC is one of the most commonly used frameworks for examining environmental performance. Kuznets first introduced it in 1955 to explain the relationship between per capita income and income inequality, represented as an inverted U-shaped curve. Over time, scholars began applying the same concept to environmental studies, and it has since become a central model for analyzing how economic growth interacts with environmental degradation. This shift significantly shaped the direction of environmental discourse.

According to the EKC hypothesis, environmental degradation tends to worsen during the early stages of economic growth but begins to decline once income exceeds a certain threshold. This suggests that as households or nations become wealthier, they may initially produce more waste due to higher consumption and increased reliance on packaged and disposable products. However, with further economic advancement, waste generation per person may decline. This reduction is often linked to rising environmental awareness, shifts toward more sustainable and eco-friendly consumption patterns, and greater investment in modern waste management technologies and recycling infrastructure.

Relevance of Theory to the Study

The EKC theory is highly relevant to this study because it underscores how income inequality shapes the patterns of waste generation. Households with varying income levels contribute differently to the waste stream, making policies that address these disparities necessary. For example, reducing inequality can promote more equitable access to effective waste management services. Moreover, public education across all socioeconomic levels is crucial in raising awareness about the environmental impacts of consumption habits. Investment in waste management infrastructure, such as recycling facilities and composting systems, is essential for promoting sustainable practices and advancing a circular economy.

The empirical evidence further supports the usefulness of this framework. Sarkodie and Ozturk (2020), in their study of climate change mitigation and environmental quality in Kenya, tested the EKC hypothesis's validity by integrating energy efficiency and consumption indicators. Their findings add depth to the debate on the applicability of the EKC in developing contexts. Likewise, Rashid, Viswanathan, and Hassan (2018) critically reviewed the global relevance of the theory, warning that the "grow now, clean later" approach associated with the EKC may be too resource-intensive, carrying environmental costs that the planet might not be able to absorb in the long run.

The WMH provides another important framework for thinking about sustainable waste practices. Waste prevention is prioritized above all else, followed by reuse, recycling, recovery, and disposal as a last resort. This

hierarchy not only guides decision-making at the individual and institutional levels but also encourages a fundamental rethinking of how societies interact with waste, emphasizing what is most beneficial for the environment.

At the top of the hierarchy is reduction, which focuses on minimizing waste generation at its source. This can be achieved through strategies such as buying materials with minimal packaging, avoiding single-use goods, opting for recyclable or repairable items, and managing inventory to prevent food spoilage. While higher socioeconomic status (SES) often correlates with greater consumption, it can also provide the resources and awareness needed to adopt effective waste reduction practices.

Reuse extends the life of materials by treating them as resources rather than as discards. Reuse may be driven by necessity for lower-income households, while higher-income households may reuse items out of environmental consciousness. Reuse reduces the need for new production, lessening the strain on natural resources, energy, and the environment, while also helping to cut greenhouse gas emissions (Rückert, Balkute, & Dornack, 2024).

The next step is recycling, which includes converting discarded materials into new goods. Although recycling is good, it ranks lower than reduction and reuse because it requires considerable resource inputs, such as energy and water. For example, recycling scrap paper consumes considerable resources to produce new paper. Effective recycling depends on access to infrastructure such as collection systems and processing facilities. Households with higher SES are generally more able to participate in recycling because they often have better access to such infrastructure (Hemidat et al., 2022).

At the bottom of the hierarchy is disposal, which remains the most widely used but least desirable method. This includes open dumping, landfilling, or incineration without energy recovery. These practices are unsustainable because the waste left in landfills continues to generate harmful environmental impacts over time. SES also influences disposal patterns, as higher-income households tend to have access to more structured waste collection systems, whereas lower-income households often rely on unsafe or informal disposal methods (Kaza et al., 2018). Empirical research reinforces this model's value. Barbara and Sabine (2024), along with Nor, Nurain, Suriani, Nurhidayah, Nisha, and Alia (2021), examined the waste hierarchy in practice and confirmed its central principle: waste management strategies should aim to move "up the hierarchy" toward reduction, reuse, and recycling (the 3Rs), and away from disposal. This highlights the importance of prioritizing strategies that minimize waste generation while maximizing resource recovery.

2.4 Empirical Literature Review

Research on the relationship between socioeconomic characteristics and household garbage output has received a lot of attention recently. Zhao et al. (2021) discovered that economic growth and urbanization had a significant impact on waste management practices in Sri Lanka, providing a framework for understanding how social and economic dynamics influence trash behaviors. Broader research has also examined how community views and cultural norms influence trash generation patterns, emphasizing the social aspect of waste practices (Social Factors Influencing Household Waste Management, 2022).

In Chennai, India, Ashutosh, Vasanth, and Karthigaiselvan (2024) and Deshpande (2024) revealed that household income is a crucial factor in determining waste generation. Interestingly, lower-income households were found to produce more waste, often because of reliance on low-cost, single-use products. Education also plays a vital role, as households with higher education levels were more likely to participate in recycling activities. Both

studies emphasized that income disparities and educational differences must be addressed to design effective waste management strategies.

Other regional studies support these conclusions. Siregar and Putra (2023) discovered a strong relationship between the socioeconomic level and the effectiveness of waste management in Mandau.

District, emphasizing the importance of customizing solutions to local circumstances. On a global scale, Velis (2023) applied machine learning to assess the relationship between socioeconomic development and waste management in cities, concluding that higher economic development is generally associated with more efficient systems.

Research has also examined specific waste streams. Sukendi, Putra, and Agrina (2023) studied medical waste in Southeast Asia, drawing attention to ecological and socioeconomic challenges in its sustainable management. Similarly, Tafesse, Girma, and Dessalegn (2022) analyzed construction waste and emphasized its dual economic and environmental impacts. Denise (2022) found that urbanization strongly contributes to household waste generation in Sierra, Bolivia, while Fadhullah (2022) highlighted that in East Coast Malaysia, most household waste consists of food debris and plastics, with little separation for recycling.

Latin American studies provide further insights. Hidalgo (2019) reported that in Guayaquil, Ecuador, waste composition differs significantly according to socioeconomic status, with income and occupation serving as key determinants. José, Jorge, Freddy, and César (2019) applied stratified random sampling and OLS regression to estimate household waste generation and found that organic waste dominated household solid waste composition at 72.6%, followed by plastics, glass, metals, and paper.

Other studies point to the importance of social and behavioral factors. Apolonio and Lacaza (2022) examined how community norms shape household food waste behaviors, while Han et al. (2018) explored how household characteristics in developing countries influence domestic waste patterns. Shaghayegh and Mahdi (2023), using survey data from 66 households in Iran, confirmed that employment, household size, and education significantly affect recycling and food waste generation, though they found no link between waste management knowledge and plastic waste generation.

Cosimo and Pasquale (2022) conducted an international study of Switzerland utilizing dynamic autoregressive distributed lags (D ARDL) and fuzzy cognitive maps, demonstrating that both municipal waste and economic growth influence greenhouse gas emissions in the short and long term. Their research demonstrates how education and awareness initiatives, as well as increased producer accountability, can effectively reduce waste-related emissions. Similarly, Fehr et al. (2020) investigated transitional economies and emphasized the need for integrated and context-specific waste management solutions.

Finally, research in Nigeria has provided further evidence of the socioeconomic influence on waste generation. Omekwe et al. (2023) revealed significant differences across zones in Port Harcourt, where wealthier and more educated households generated more waste but managed it better, whereas poverty and illiteracy were strongly associated with improper disposal and packaging practices. These findings reinforce the conclusion that income, education, and employment are critical determinants of household waste generation and management outcomes.

2.2.4.1 Summary of the Literature Review

The examined research shows that socioeconomic factors influence household and municipal solid waste generation, composition, and management strategies. Income consistently emerges as a primary determinant, with higher-income households generally producing larger volumes of waste, particularly packaging and disposable

items, whereas lower-income households generate more organic waste but often lack access to proper disposal and recycling facilities (Ashutosh, Vasanth, & Karthigaiselvan, 2024; Deshpande, 2024; Omekwe et al., 2023). Education is also highly linked to waste behavior, with more educated households engaging in recycling and sustainable activities (Kala, Bolia, & Sushil, 2020; Shaghayegh & Mahdi, 2023). Employment status and household size further influence both the quantity and type of waste generated, although findings on whether larger households generate more waste per capita vary (Kaza et al., 2019; Jamialahmadi, Hashem, & Jalili, 2022). Regional and international studies have reinforced these patterns. Research from India, Ecuador, Malaysia, and Nigeria highlights the complex interplay of income, education, urbanization, and social norms in shaping waste management challenges (Amaya et al., 2019; Hidalgo, 2019; Fadhullah, 2022; Omekwe *et al.*, 2023). Studies from developed contexts, such as Switzerland and global comparative analyses, show that higher levels of socioeconomic development often coincide with more effective waste management systems, largely due to stronger institutional frameworks, technology adoption, and CEPs (Cosimo & Pasquale, 2022; Velis, 2023). Beyond household waste, specialized streams such as construction and medical waste highlight additional socioeconomic and environmental pressures, particularly in rapidly urbanizing and transitional economies (Sukendi, Putra, & Agrina, 2023; Tafesse, Girma, & Dessalegn, 2022). The literature also underscores the health, environmental, and social implications of waste mismanagement, with poverty and illiteracy emerging as critical barriers to sustainable practices (Donald, Godwin, Simon, & Jude, 2021; Omekwe et al., 2023). Therefore, effective policies must integrate economic, educational, and social considerations, supported by infrastructure investment and public awareness. The need for inclusive and adaptive waste management strategies is evident, particularly in contexts where rapid urbanization and inequality intensify waste-related challenges.

3. Methods and Materials used

3.1 Study Area

Location and Size: Jalingo, the capital of Taraba State, is located between latitude 8°47' and 9°01'N and longitude 11°22' and 11°30'E (Fig. 1). It is bordered by Lau Local Government Area (LGA) to the north, Yorro LGA to the east, and Ardo-Kola LGA to the south and west. The city covers a total land area of approximately 204,073 km² and lies at an altitude of approximately 351 m above sea level.

The relief of Jalingo shows an undulating plain interspersed with mountain ranges. These ranges extend from the Kona area through the boundary between the Jalingo and Lau LGAs and continue southward to the Yorro and Ardo-Kola LGAs, forming a circular configuration that extends toward the Gongon area (Taraba State Ministry of Land and Survey, 2024).

Figure 1: Study area map (Source: Taraba Geographic Information System TAGIS)

Climate of the Study Area: Jalingo Local Government Area (LGA) experiences a tropical continental climate, characterized by distinct wet and dry seasons. The wet season typically begins in April and extends until October, whereas the dry season runs from November to March. The area records a mean annual rainfall of approximately 1,200 mm and an average annual temperature of approximately 29°C. Relative humidity ranges between 60% and 70% during the wet season but drops to around 35%–45% during the dry season (Taraba State Ministry of Agriculture, 2024).

Relief and Drainage: The relief of Jalingo Local Government Area consists of an undulating plain interspersed with mountain ranges. This compact massif of rocky outcrops extends from the Kona area through the boundary between the Jalingo and Lau LGAs and down to the Yorro and Ardo-Kola LGAs. The ranges form a circular configuration that extends to the Gongon area, giving the landscape a semicircular, shield-like appearance that provides a natural barrier to Jalingo town (Taraba State Ministry of Agriculture, 2024).

Jalingo Metropolis is drained by two major rivers, Mayogwoi and Lamurde, both of which originate from the mountain ranges in Yorro LGA and ultimately discharge into the Benue River system at Tau village. Alongside smaller streams, these rivers form the drainage basin of Jalingo, playing a crucial role in the study area's hydrology (Taraba State Ministry of Agriculture, 2024).

The relief and drainage patterns in Jalingo significantly influence settlement, agricultural activity, and waste disposal. The relatively flat plains provide favorable conditions for urban expansion, farming, and transportation. The fertile floodplains along the river courses support intensive agricultural practices, while the availability of surface water sustains both domestic and commercial uses. However, these same features also pose challenges: settlements clustered near rivers are vulnerable to flooding, which can intensify the spread of improperly disposed household waste into waterways. Similarly, waste dumping on slopes and in low-lying areas often leads to water

source leachate contamination, posing risks to public health and environmental quality. Thus, the interaction between physical geography and human activity in Jalingo directly shapes the waste management challenges of the city.

Geology and Soil: The geology of Jalingo comprises diverse rock formations and soil types that shape the landscape and influence the area's natural resource base. The region is endowed with mineral deposits, such as limestone, gypsum, and kaolin, which are of economic importance for construction, agriculture, and other industrial activities (Taraba State Ministry of Land and Survey, 2024).

The soils of Jalingo are typical of the West African tropical belt, comprising primarily ferruginous, ferralitic, and lateritic soils. These soils are rich in iron and aluminum oxides, which give them their reddish-brown color and often result in acidic conditions. While fertile enough to support agriculture, the soils are generally sandy or gravelly in texture, making them susceptible to erosion and flooding (Taraba State Ministry of Land and Survey, 2024). Agricultural production thrives on these soils, with yams, beans, maize, and sorghum being widely cultivated in the area.

Jalingo lies within the Northern Guinea Savanna Zone, which is characterized by grasses interspersed with tall trees and shrubs. However, this natural vegetation cover is gradually declining because of urban expansion and physical development. Common tree species in the region include eucalyptus, teak, neem, shea butter, baobab, acacia, and silk cotton. The vegetation also provides habitats for various wildlife species, including birds, antelopes, and reptiles (Taraba State Ministry of Agriculture, 2024).

The geology, soils, and vegetation of Jalingo have direct implications for environmental management and sustainability. Improper waste disposal in low-lying areas can worsen soil erosion and flooding, driven by the fragile soil texture, leading to leachate contamination of water and agricultural lands. Mineral resource exploitation, while economically beneficial, increases land demand and contributes to habitat loss. Similarly, the continuous decline in vegetation cover due to urban expansion not only reduces biodiversity but also limits the natural capacity of the environment to absorb waste and pollutants. These interrelated factors underscore the importance of integrating land use planning, resource management, and sustainable waste practices into Jalingo's urban development policies.

Socio-Economic Activities: The economy of Jalingo, Taraba State, Nigeria, is diverse and sustained by multiple sectors that contribute to local livelihoods and development. Agriculture remains a major economic activity in Jalingo, supported by fertile soils and a favorable climate. The principal crops cultivated include maize, rice, yam, cassava, and various vegetables (Taraba State Ministry of Agriculture, 2024).

Livestock rearing is also significant, with cattle, sheep, and goats being the dominant animals raised. The availability of extensive grazing lands supports this activity, making it an important contributor to household incomes and food security (Taraba State Ministry of Agriculture, 2024).

Jalingo is the commercial hub of Taraba State. Local markets such as Kasuwan Bera and Jalingo Main Market are central to trading activities, facilitating the exchange of goods and services within the metropolis and neighboring areas (Taraba State Ministry of Agriculture, 2024).

Jalingo artisans engage in weaving, pottery, leatherwork, and beadwork, contributing to the local economy through the production and sale of handicrafts. These artisanal activities provide employment and help preserve cultural heritage (Taraba State Ministry of Agriculture, 2024). However, the diversity of such socio-economic activities has contributed to increased waste generation within the metropolis.

The services sector plays a crucial role, encompassing banking, education, healthcare, transportation, and hospitality. The city hosts financial institutions, educational establishments, health care facilities, hotels, and transport services that cater to the growing population's needs (Taraba State Ministry of Agriculture, 2024). As the capital of Taraba State, Jalingo functions as the administrative and political center, hosting government offices, agencies, and public institutions that drive governance and economic activities related to administration. Collectively, these economic activities underpin livelihoods, generate income, and create employment opportunities, thereby supporting Jalingo and its surrounding areas' broader economic development. At the same time, they significantly contribute to urban waste generation. Agricultural and livestock activities produce organic waste, including crop residues, animal droppings, and food waste. Trade generates large volumes of packaging materials, plastics, and discarded goods. Artisanal and small-scale industrial activities add construction debris, leather scraps, and other non-biodegradable materials. Similarly, the service sector and government institutions contribute office waste, medical waste, and e-waste. Consequently, the interplay of these economic activities not only drives the city's growth but also intensifies Jalingo's waste management complexity, necessitating sustainable and context-specific interventions.

Population and Settlement: The population of Jalingo was estimated at 581,000 as of November 2022, with a projected annual growth rate of 3.2% (World Population Review, 2022). Approximately 72% of the city's inhabitants live in unplanned settlements, which complicates urban planning, infrastructure provision, and service delivery.

Jalingo's residents are largely farmers, traders, and career civil servants. The metropolis is ethnolinguistically diverse, with Hausa, Fulani, Kona, Mumuye, Yandang, and English widely spoken as communication languages. Despite the city's range of economic activities that could support social development, many adults remain illiterate or semi-literate, largely due to persistent poverty and limited access to education.

The population structure includes children, adults, and the elderly, with households spanning low-, middle-, and high-income brackets (World Population Review, 2022). This socioeconomic diversity influences livelihood and consumption patterns and has direct implications for waste generation. Rapid population growth, widespread poverty, and the predominance of unplanned settlements have intensified waste management challenges in Jalingo, leading to the rising volumes of poorly managed household and commercial waste. These pressures underscore the urgency of developing inclusive, sustainable, and context-specific waste management strategies.

3.2 The Research Method

This study adopted a survey research design. According to Ajai and Amuche (2015), a survey design seeks to review, investigate, and gather facts to determine and interpret the nature or status of phenomena on a large scale. It involves collecting information from a relatively large number of individuals or items that are considered representative of the wider population. The design is particularly suited for obtaining data on the current status of issues or events and for examining relationships within a large group.

The types of data required include socio-economic and waste-related data from households in Jalingo, the demographic characteristics of respondents, the effects of waste generation on households in the study area, and the factors influencing waste generation in Jalingo.

Primary data was collected using structured questionnaires, photographic documentation, and direct field observations. These methods were employed to obtain firsthand information on the relationship between households' socioeconomic status and waste generation patterns in Jalingo Metropolis.

Structured questionnaires were administered to households across different socioeconomic strata (low, middle, and high income). The questionnaire was divided into two sections. Section A presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents. Section B consists of socioeconomic factors and waste generation, which covers household income, educational level, occupation, and household size. The waste generation item comprises 40 items on a four-point scale of strongly agree (4), agree (3), disagree (2), and strongly disagree (1). Direct observations were conducted to supplement the data obtained from the questionnaires and photographs. The researcher visited selected households and neighborhoods to observe daily waste disposal practices, the presence and use of waste bins, frequency of waste collection, and environmental cleanliness. This method provided real-time insights into the actual waste generation and management practices beyond what was self-reported in the questionnaire. These combined methods ensured a comprehensive and triangulated approach to understanding the relationship between household socioeconomic status and waste generation in Jalingo.

In terms of the population of the study area, the population of Jalingo stood at 318,481 people as of November 2022, with a projected annual growth rate of 3.2% (World Population Review, 2022).

Sample size of 390 respondents was obtained using the Kriecj and Morgan table (1970) for sample determination. The researcher distributed 390 copies of the questionnaires to the selected respondents randomly selected from the residential areas of 19 communities in Jalingo metropolis. The respondents in the questionnaire were mainly households in the selected residential areas. The researcher collected the complete copies himself, so the sample used in the data analysis consisted of 384 respondents.

A multistage probability sampling procedure was used where every member of the population has a known, non-zero chance of being selected. The target population consists of all households within the Jalingo metropolis. A list of all the wards and communities within Jalingo was obtained from the National Population Commission, which served as a sample frame. The Jalingo metropolis was stratified based on low-, middle-, and high-income socioeconomic zones. This ensures that all socioeconomic classes are adequately represented. A simple random sampling technique was used to select fixed-number clusters from each socioeconomic group. A household list or numbering was used to select households from each selected cluster using systematic sampling. The inclusion criteria include households with residents who have lived in the area for at least 6 months.

Table 1: Community samples

S/N	Wards	Community	Population	Sample size
	Abbare Yelwa		4,751	10
	Yelwa			
	Sabongari, Kasuwan Rumpa, Wuron Musa			18
	Kachalla		13,037	
	Sembe			
	Maigidadi	Jauro Tella and Jauro Ila	100,894	122
3		Kona, Kishou, Murkuni, Gulum, Nukkai,	26,622	32
4	Kona	Watai		

Total: 318481 390

Source: Adapted from the NPC, Jalingo Office (2025). The data management and analysis were performed using a computer. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered using frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation to summarize the socio-economic variables and waste generation data, while the hypotheses were tested using the SPSS package version 20 linear regression. Linear regression was used to test the hypotheses at a significance level of 0.05. This is because linear regression is a common tool used for predictive analysis (Hillier, 2023). Linear regression estimate was used to describe the data and explain the extent of the relationship. Meanwhile, linear regression is an algorithm that provides a linear relationship between independent and dependent variables. The formula for a simple linear regression is as follows: $y = c + b \cdot x$, where:

y is the predicted value of the dependent variable (y) for any given independent variable (x) = (waste generation)
 B_0 is the intercept and the predicted value of y when x is 0.

B_1 is the regression coefficient—how much we expect y to change as x increases.

where x is the independent variable (the variable we expect to influence y) = (society-economic status of household)

e is the error of the estimate or the degree of variation in our estimate of the regression coefficient.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 2: Demographic characteristics of the respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percent (%)
Age of the respondents		
18-29	25	6.5
30-39	104	27.1
40-49	175	45.6
50-59	38	9.9
60 Above	42	10.9
Total	384	100.0
Gender		
Female	146	38.0
Male	239	62.0
Total	384	100.0

Table 2 shows the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The table revealed that 25 (6.5%) of the respondents were between the ages of 18 and 29 years, 104 (27.1 %) were between the ages of 30 and 39 years, 175 (45.6%) were between the ages of 40 and 49 years, 38 (9.9%) were between the ages of 50 and 59 years, and 42 (10.9%) were above 60 years, implying that most of the respondents were adult and household owners.

Objective 1: To identify the socio-economic factors influencing waste generation in Jalingo.

Table 3: Socioeconomic Factors Influencing Waste Generation in Jalingo

S/N	Socio-Economic Factors	Frequency	Percentage
1	Income Level		
A	Below 20,000	52	13.5
B	20,000-50,000	97	25.3
C	51,000-100,000	92	24.0
D	101,000-200,000	77	20.1
E	Above 200,000	66	17.2
	Total	384	100%

2 Education level

A	No formal education	34	8.9
B	Primary	22	5.7
C	Secondary	78	20.3
D	Tertiary	187	48.7
E	Postgraduate	63	16.4
	Total	384	100%

3 Occupation

A	Unemployed	25	6.5
B	Self-employed	58	15.1
C	Public sector	196	51
D	Farmer	68	17.7
E	Retired	37	9.6
	Total	384	100%

4 Household size

A	1-3	116	30.1
B	4-6	126	32.8
C	7-9	88	22.9
D	10 above	54	14.1
	Total	384	100%

Source: 2025 fieldwork

Table 3 shows the socio-economic factors influencing waste generation in Jalingo. The table reveals the socio-economic factors influencing waste generation, including income level, educational level, occupation, and household size. The table shows that 52 (13.5%) of the respondents' income level is below 20,000, 97 (25.3%) of the respondents' income level is between 20,000 and 50,000, 92 (24.0%) income level is between 51,000 and 100,000, 77 (20.1%) earn between 101,000 and 200,000, while 66 (17.2%) income level is above 200,000. Table 3 shows that 34 (8.9%) of the respondents had no formal education, 22 (5.7%) attended primary school, 78 (20.3%) attended secondary school, 187 (48.7%) attended tertiary education, and 63 (16.4%) are post graduate.

Table 3 also shows the occupational level of the respondents. The table revealed that 25 (6.5%) of the respondents are unemployed, 58 (15.1%) are self-employed, 196 (51%) are public sector workers, 68 (17.7%) are farmers, and 37 (9.6%) are retired civil servants.

The table finally revealed that 116 (30.1%) of the respondents household size range of 1-3, 126 (32.8%) ranged from 4 to 6. 88 (22.9%) households ranged from 7 to 9 while 54 (14.1%) had household members above 10.

Objective 2: To investigate the influence of household income level on waste generation in Jalingo Metropolis and the level of waste generation in Jalingo Metropolis.

Table 4: Mean Responses on Income Level of a Household Influenced by Waste Generation in Jalingo Metropolis. N=384

S/N	ITEMS	Mean	SD	Remark
1	The amount of waste generated in my household has increased as our income has increased.	3.69	0.58	Agree
2	Higher income allows my household to purchase more packaged goods, resulting in more plastic waste.	3.47	0.71	Agree
3	We generate more food waste because we can afford a variety of fresh food items.	3.61	0.62	Agree
4	My household produces more electronic waste (e.g., gadgets and appliances) as our income level increases.	3.69	0.57	Agree
5	Our income level allows us to afford proper waste disposal services (e.g., paying for garbage collection).	3.69	0.53	Agree
6	We are more likely to recycle and sort our waste because we can afford to do so.	3.55	0.71	Agree
7	Higher income enables us to donate or repurpose items instead of discarding them as waste.	3.72	0.56	Agree
8	The income level of our household influences our purchasing decisions, leading to approximately waste.	3.57	0.63	Agree
9	We tend to buy in bulk or choose disposable items, leading to more waste, because we can afford it.	3.80	0.4	Agree
10	Our income level allows us to choose products with minimal packaging to reduce waste.	3.45	0.67	Agree
	Grand mean	3.62	0.60	

Source: Fieldwork (2025)

Table 4 shows that income level influences waste generation in the Jalingo metropolis. All items had a mean higher than the fixed mean of 2.5. The grand mean of 3.62 with a standard deviation of 0.60 suggests that most of the respondents' income level determines the level of waste generated. We tend to buy in bulk or choose disposable items, leading to more waste, because we can afford it. The highest mean score (mean = 3.8, SD = 0.4) was recorded for the amount of waste generated by households as their income increased, indicating that the higher the income level, the higher the rate of buying items that could lead to waste generation.

HO₁: No significant influence of household income level on waste generation in Jalingo Metropolis.

Table 5: Regression analysis on the influence of household income level on waste generation in Jalingo Metropolis

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error in the Estimate
1	.130 ^a	.017	.014	2.92935

a. Predictors: (Constant), Income Level_1

ANOVA^a						
Model	Sum of the Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
Regression	1:56.277 3277.970	1	56.277	6.558	.011 ^b	
Residual		382	8.581			
Total	3334.247	383				

a. Dependent variable: Waste generation_1

b. Predictors: (Constant), Income level

The regression analysis in Table 5 shows that household income level has a significant effect on waste generation in Jalingo Metropolis. The model summary produced an R value of 0.130, indicating a positive relationship between income and waste generation. The R² value of 0.17 indicates that income level explains approximately 17% of the variation in household waste generation.

The ANOVA results in Table 5 confirm the statistical significance of the regression model (F = 6.558, p < 0.05). This means that the effect of income on waste generation is unlikely to be due to chance. Since the p-value (0.011) is below the 0.05 threshold, the null hypothesis of no significant influence is rejected. Therefore, the study concludes that household income plays a significant role in determining the volume of waste generated in Jalingo.

Objective 3: To assess the relationship between household members' education level and their waste management practices in Jalingo Metropolis.

Table 6: Mean Responses on Education Level of a Household Influenced by Waste Generation in Jalingo Metropolis. N=384

S/N	ITEMS	mean	SD	Remark
1	My education level has made me more aware of waste's environmental impact.	3.24	.96	
2	Members of my household separate recyclable waste (e.g., paper, plastic, glass) from non-recyclable waste.	3.34	.95	
3	Thanks to our education level, we have a clear understanding of which materials can be recycled.	3.32	.87	
4	Higher education levels in my household lead to more consistent recycling practices.	3.10	1.03	

5	My household is more likely to use formal waste disposal services (e.g., paying for garbage collection) because of our education level.	3.42	.76
6	We avoid improper waste disposal methods (e.g., open burning and illegal dumping) due to our educational background.	2.77	1.11
7	Education has made participants more likely to participate in community waste management initiatives (e.g., clean-up campaigns).	3.36	.89
8	My household actively seeks ways to reduce waste (e.g., buying in bulk and using reusable items) due to our education level.	3.29	.98
9	We are more likely to repurpose or donate items than to throw them away, thanks to our education.	3.01	1.02
10	Higher levels of education have encouraged us to adopt practices that minimize waste generation.	3.28	.78
Grand Mean		3.21	.93

Table 6 shows the mean and standard deviation of the relationship between household members' education level and their waste management practices in Jalingo Metropolis. All the items had a mean higher than the fixed mean of 2.5 with a grand mean of 3.21 and a standard deviation of .93.

This shows that there is a high level of agreement on the education level of household members and their waste management practices. The highest mean recorded was 3.42, indicating that households are more likely to use formal disposal services (such as paying for garbage collection) because of their education level. The result generally reviewed that household members' waste management level could be determined by their educational level.

HO₂: There is no significant relationship between household members' education level and their waste management practices in Jalingo Metropolis.

Table 7: Regression analysis on the relationship between household members' education level and their waste management practices in Jalingo Metropolis.

Model Summary

Model R R Square Adjusted R Std. Error in the Estimate
Square

1	.428 ^a	.183	.181	3.07878
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a. Predictors: (Constant), Education Level_2

ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of the Squares	Df	Mean F Square	Sig.
Regression	813.557	1	813.557	85.828
1Residual	3620.933	382	9.479	.000 ^b
Total	4434.490	383		

a. Dependent variable: Waste generation_2

b. Predictors: (Constant), Education Level

The regression analysis in Table 7 indicates a significant relationship between household members' education level and their waste management practices in Jalingo Metropolis. The model produced an R value of 0.428, indicating a positive association between education and waste management practices. The R² value of 0.183 further suggests that approximately 18% of the variations in waste management practices can be explained by education level.

The ANOVA results in Table 7 confirm the statistical significance of the regression model ($F = 85.828, p < 0.05$). This means that the relationship between education and waste management practices is not a result of chance. Since the p-value (0.000) is below the 0.05 threshold, the null hypothesis of no significant influence is rejected. Therefore, the study concludes that education level has a meaningful effect on the way households in Jalingo Metropolis manage their waste.

The analysis showed that household income level has a strong influence on waste generation in Jalingo. Both the mean analysis and regression results confirmed that income is a major factor that influences the volume of waste produced. This finding is consistent with earlier studies. For example, Ashutosh, Vasanth, and Karthigaiselvan (2024) reported that monthly income plays a central role in determining waste generation patterns, noting that low-income households often produce more waste due to their dependence on inexpensive single-use products. Similarly, Deshpande (2024) identified income as a key driver in Chennai, while Omekwe et al. (2023) found that households with higher incomes and higher education in low-density neighborhoods generated more waste than those in more densely populated areas. These results also agree with the findings of Kaza, Yao, Bhada Tata, and Woerden (2019), Teferi (2022), and Jamialahmadi, Hashem, and Jalili (2022), who emphasized income as a critical socioeconomic factor influencing both the volume and composition of household waste.

In addition to income, education level emerged as another significant factor influencing waste management practices in Jalingo. The results indicated a strong relationship between household members' educational attainment and their waste management approaches.

Households with higher education levels tended to adopt better disposal and recycling practices. Ashutosh et al. (2024) supported this outcome, demonstrating that education predicts recycling behavior, with educated households showing higher recycling rates. Deshpande (2024) and Omekwe et al. (2023) reached similar conclusions, whereas Kala, Bolia, and Sushil (2020) established a positive correlation between education and waste generation. Shaghayegh and Mahdi

(2023) also confirmed that education levels significantly influence waste practices, underscoring the importance of awareness and education campaigns in promoting sustainable waste management.

5. Conclusions and Recommendations

This study explored how households' socioeconomic status (SES) affects waste generation in Jalingo Metropolis, Taraba State. The study concludes that socioeconomic status is a key factor that influences household waste generation and disposal practices in Jalingo. Income level and education level significantly influence both the volume and type of waste produced. Households with higher incomes were found to generate larger quantities of non-biodegradable waste, such as plastics and packaging materials, whereas lower income households often face difficulties in proper waste disposal due to limited access to collection services and dependence on basic disposal methods.

These findings indicate that a uniform strategy cannot solve the waste management problems in Jalingo. Instead, solutions should be tailored to the specific socioeconomic conditions of different household groups. Priority measures include improving education and public awareness, expanding access to organized waste collection systems, and promoting sustainable consumption patterns.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

- i. The Taraba State Ministry of Waste Management and Innovation should work closely with the Jalingo Local Government Council to develop and implement waste management policies that reflect the distinct waste generation and disposal behaviors of different socioeconomic groups in the Jalingo Metropolis. By 2026, local authorities should establish a policy framework that categorizes interventions according to income level, occupation, and household size.
- ii. By 2027, the Jalingo Local Government Authority should ensure that at least 50% of high-income households adopt sustainable practices, such as reducing single-use plastics, reusing items, and composting organic waste. This can be achieved by providing incentives (e.g., tax rebates) while simultaneously expanding waste collection points and establishing at least three new recycling centers in low-income areas.
- iii. The Jalingo Local Government Authority should launch a continuous public awareness campaign by 2026 that target schools, community associations, and markets in the Jalingo Metropolis by 2026. The LGA's project team will measure success by achieving at least a 30% increase in household participation in recycling programs and proper waste disposal within 3 years.

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